

EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT: USING INTERNET TECHNOLOGIES IN ENGLISH CLASSES TO IMPROVE THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article explores the ways and methods of using Internet technologies in English lessons.

Key words: internet technologies, English lesson, resources, sites, teacher, student.

Аннотация. В данной статье исследуются способы и методы использования интернет – технологий на уроках английского языка.

Ключевые слова: интернет – технологии, урок английского языка, ресурсы, сайты, учитель, учащийся.

“We need technology in every classroom and in every student and teacher’s hand, because it is the pen and paper of our time, and it is the lens through which we experience much of our world.” – David Warlick

The increasing demand for multilingual communication in today's globalized world has made foreign language learning a vital necessity for individuals in various fields. While traditional classroom-based methods of language learning still serve their purpose, advances in technology have presented a new era of opportunities for effective language learning. The use of modern IT tools such as mobile applications, online platforms, and multimedia software has become a significant part of the foreign language learning process

Modern IT tools have become an essential component of language learning and instruction as a result of the rapid advancement of technology. The use of technology in language learning provides a number of advantages, including increasing the speed and effectiveness of language learning, raising learners' motivation and engagement, giving them access to real materials, and allowing them to interact with native speakers. [7]

In the current era of globalization and technological growth, the role of IT in language learning is essential. Traditional language learning techniques have undergone a substantial transformation because to modern IT resources, which have increased interaction, accessibility, and interest.

Furthermore, information technology tools have made it easier for language teachers to administer language tests, evaluate students' performance, and provide feedback. This information assists learners in identifying areas for improvement and adjusting their learning tactics accordingly.

The successful integration of IT in language learning, on the other hand, is based on the effective application of appropriate approaches and strategies. Teachers must understand the needs of their students, establish clear learning objectives and goals, and select appropriate IT solutions that correspond with the course objectives.[6]

Nowadays, the role of foreign languages becomes indispensable. Knowledge of foreign languages makes it possible to join to the world culture, to use the full potential of the Internet resources. New information technologies are being intensively introduced into all spheres of our

life, including the educational process. New informational educational technology becomes the part of the educational process. The applying Internet opportunities in foreign language classes is an important piece in the methodology, which requires new approaches and innovative solutions

Due to the number of English learners are increasing different teaching methods have been implemented to test the effectiveness in the teaching process. At present, the onset of technology has drastically changed the old manners of teaching English. With the influence of the phenomenon called Globalization which is interrelated with technology, education work and culture have been affected positively. The applying Internet opportunities in foreign language classes is an important piece in the methodology, which requires new approaches and innovative solutions .[1]

Today people can say that the Net technology is the part of the general information culture of students and pedagogues. The Internet stimulates the desire of children to learn, expands the area of individual activity of each student, increases the speed of supplying quality material at one lesson. The issue of integrating the Internet into education and its use in teaching foreign languages is currently quite relevant, as with the use of the Internet as a means of teaching a foreign language, many goals and objectives of training and education can be realized as well as possible.

Combination of information technology with the project method allows students to practically apply their knowledge and skills, and therefore is one of the forms of organization of research and cognitive activity , in which cooperative collective activities are successfully implemented, allowing to increase the motivation of learning foreign languages .[3]

Applying of Internet resources in an English class makes it possible to achieve stable positive results. The use of Internet resources at the English lesson is relevant today, because the teacher must be interesting for his students, improve their pedagogical skills and level of intelligence .

The possibilities of applying Internet sources are tremendous. Global Internet network creates the conditions for obtaining any necessary information for teachers and students : news from the life of young people, articles from newspapers and magazines, regional geographic material, necessary literature, etc. Students can take part in testing, quizzes, contests, competitions, held on the Internet, chat with peers from other countries, participate in video conferences, etc. Students can receive information on the problem they are currently working on in the project. [2]

The Internet can promote education in any place, at any time for any purpose, therefore it is the most powerful new formation in the educational sphere of the whole world .

The information revolution expanded access to education in terms of the amount of information needed and data processing.

Interactive Internet technology is revolutionizing the learning model, as it is a powerful tool for educational change .

The Internet is an enormous bank of information of different sizes, formats, content and topics from around the world. Nowadays, the Internet is the most convenient, and therefore a popular source of information in all spheres of life for any contingent of people . Therefore, it is not surprising that the Internet is widely used in education.

A great number of sites are devoted to varied topics, areas of education, so the Internet is indispensable for both students and teachers.

The most popular search engines at the moment are:

- <http://google.com>
- <http://yandex.ru>

- <http://mail.ru>
- <http://www.yahoo.com>

Despite the diversity of the forms of information presented on the Internet, which can be in the format of video or audio, etc., reading on the network remains the most basic activity or form of work, since most of the information is still presented in the form of text documents. Therefore, the Internet in the classroom is most often used by the teacher to develop reading skills. Reading on the Internet is a review of the necessary information, since there is a lot of information on the Internet, therefore when using the Internet, the skill of viewing reading is mainly used. Moreover, websites containing any text are colorfully decorated with related pictures or other visual supports, like video or animation .[5]

A lesson with the use of Internet technologies is built on the basis of a three-phase structure of a lesson:

1. Preparatory stage
2. Work online (work on the Internet)
3. Work offline

Modernity imposes ever-increasing demands on the teaching of practical foreign language skills in everyday communication and professional life. The capacity of information is growing and the routine ways of its transfer, storage and processing are ineffective. The use of information technology opens up the enormous possibilities of a computer as a means of training.

Without the use of Internet technology in the educational process, it is difficult to imagine modern English lessons. Internet technologies contribute to the enhancement of students' cognitive activity, increases interest in learning languages, students have the opportunity to get acquainted with the realities of the country of the language being studied in a bright, interesting way to test their skills in interactive activities.

However, it is important to acknowledge that the achievements we witnessed are the result of the collective efforts of our skilled educators, who skillfully guided the learning process and facilitated meaningful interactions. In conclusion, the commendable test results obtained at the end of the school quarter provide compelling evidence of the significant progress made by our students in their language skills and abilities. The integration of YouTube and Kahoot, coupled with comprehensive instruction, has played a vital role in shaping and enhancing their language proficiency. As we continue to explore innovative approaches and technologies, we remain dedicated to optimizing language instruction and meeting the evolving needs of our students .[8]

The use of information technology, including platforms, significantly improves the effectiveness of foreign language learning skills and abilities.

An experiment was conducted to confirm that the use of information technology, especially platforms, provides more effective opportunities to build foreign language skills and abilities. The experiment was divided into two phases in order to compare the results and evaluate the benefits that were obtained using the platforms.

The first phase of the experiment included lessons using information technology such as YouTube and Kahoot. Students accessed educational videos on YouTube that complemented the topics covered in the textbooks and allowed them to improve their pronunciation, vocabulary, and understanding of grammatical concepts. In addition, the Kahoot platform provided interactive quizzes and games to help test students' understanding and reinforce their knowledge. This phase allowed us to assess the impact of using the platforms on student engagement and motivation.

The second phase of the experiment consisted of traditional lessons without the use of information technology. Here, students mastered the same topics and grammar rules, but without access to educational videos and interactive games. This phase served to compare results and determine the difference in student achievement with and without the use of information technology.

The aim of the experiment was to confirm that the use of information technology, including platforms, significantly improves the effectiveness of foreign language learning skills and abilities. By conducting the experiment in two stages, we aimed to compare the results and identify the advantages of using platforms for learning .

The Internet at the lesson contributed to the development of the entire educational process and allows you to train and educate students whose education fully meets the requirements of modern society.

However, we must not forget Internet technology is only an auxiliary technical tool of training, probably, the most important thing for an instructor in the up-to-date world of virtual realities, first of all, to remain a Man!

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